

PAY WHAT YOU WANT

Exploring Client-driven Determination of Therapy Costs

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ABSTRACT

Access to affordable and accessible mental health care remains a challenge for many Indians, leading to a significant care gap — the difference between the care patients require and available healthcare practices. In India, the care gap for severe and common mental illnesses surpasses 70% and is further exacerbated by marginalization.

Private mental health professionals often address affordability concerns by offering sliding scales or waiving fees, but this requires clients to disclose their income information. To overcome this obstacle, The Alternative Story, a Bengaluru-based organization, introduced the Pay-What-You-Want (PWYW) initiative, allowing clients to determine the amount they can pay for counselling sessions, starting at Rs. 299.

This paper explores the impact of the PWYW initiative on therapy recipients and proposes it as a viable solution to bridge the care gap. The study highlights the initiative's significant benefits for marginalized individuals, particularly those with at least one marginalized identity and those who self-finance their therapy.

Keywords: mental healthcare, affordability, accessibility, Indian healthcare

Introduction

The care gap in India reveals a distressing reality: the majority of individuals in need of mental health care do not have access to it, either due to its unavailability, unaffordability, or lack of accessibility. This glaring disparity between the care required and the care provided has severe consequences for the well-being of many Indians.

The care gap in India for common mental illnesses ranges from 85% to 95%, while for severe mental illnesses it stands at a staggering 70% to 90% (Kaur & Pathak, 2017). These figures highlight the urgent need for transformative solutions to bridge this gap and ensure that mental health care is within reach for all.

Scale of the Mental Health Crisis

The magnitude of the mental health crisis in India is underscored by alarming statistics. The World Health Organization (WHO) conducted a survey revealing that India has the highest number of people living with depression among WHO member countries, and ranks second for the prevalence of anxiety disorders (Mental Health Atlas 2017, 2018).

Another study estimated that approximately 197.3 lakh individuals in India suffer from mental disorders, including 45.7 lakhs with depressive disorders and 44.9 lakhs with anxiety disorders (Sagar et al., 2020). These findings demonstrate that one in seven Indians carries the burden of mental illness, underlining the pressing need for comprehensive mental health care support.

Even before the COVID-19 pandemic, the WHO predicted that by 2020 around 20% of India’s population would be affected by mental illness (Birla, 2019). The pandemic has only exacerbated the situation, with global studies reporting a surge in anxiety, depression, and stress symptoms worldwide (Rajkumar, 2020). Vulnerable populations — including individuals with pre-existing mental disorders, women, frontline workers, and those with livelihood losses — are particularly at risk (Kunzler et al., 2021; Rathore & Khanna, 2021).

Table 1
Key Mental Health Metrics in India

Mental Health Metric	Figure
Care gap – common mental illnesses	85–95%
Care gap – severe mental illnesses	70–90%
Individuals with mental disorders	~197.3 lakh
Mental health workers per 1,00,000 people (India)	1.93
Global average mental health workers per 1,00,000	9
Avg. cost of counselling session (metro cities)	Rs. 300 – Rs. 4,000
Govt. allocation to mental health (total health budget)	1.3%

Structural Barriers to Care

The current landscape of mental health care in India presents numerous challenges. Foremost, resource allocation for mental health remains woefully inadequate. A mere 1.3% of the government's total health expenditure is dedicated to mental health, with the 2020–21 budget allotting only Rs. 40 crores to the National Mental Health Programme — significantly lower than the estimated Rs. 94,073 crore required to implement the Mental Healthcare Act (Goyal, 2020).

The scarcity of mental health professionals compounds the problem. India has only 1.93 mental health workers per 1,00,000 people, far below the global average of 9 (Dhillon, 2020). Apart from Kerala — which met the WHO requirement of 1 psychiatrist per 1,00,000 people — all other states failed to provide an adequate number of mental health professionals (Joshi & Sharma, 2020). Mental health services are also predominantly concentrated in urban areas, resulting in severely limited availability in rural India (Koshy & Perappadan, 2018).

Affordability presents an additional barrier. The average cost of a counselling session in metropolitan cities ranges from Rs. 300 to Rs. 4,000, with an average of Rs. 1,500 (Desai, 2019; Sharma, 2019). Given that the average income in India is approximately Rs. 1,43,391 per annum, allocating around Rs. 6,000 per month for four to five therapy sessions is financially unfeasible for most Indians (Express News Service, 2021). There is no insurance coverage for outpatient mental health procedures, making therapy entirely an out-of-pocket expense.

Existing Affordability Approaches and Their Limitations

Some private practitioners offer free therapy services or sliding scale payments based on a client's economic circumstances (Walsh & Dasenbrook, 2008). However, sliding scales have faced criticism for potentially charging clients the highest amount they can afford, and the decision to offer reduced fees rests solely with the professional. Moreover, clients are usually responsible for initiating the request for sliding scale payments, creating additional barriers to accessing affordable care and requiring disclosure of sensitive income information.

The Pay-What-You-Want Initiative

As an alternative to sliding scales, The Alternative Story — a private organization in Bengaluru — developed an initiative called Pay What You Want (PWYW). This initiative allows clients to pay as much as they can afford, starting at a base price of Rs. 299 per session, without the need for income-based disclosures.

The organization dedicates approximately one-third of its therapy slots each month to PWYW sessions, ensuring accessibility for a broader range of individuals. The PWYW initiative has been in operation since the organization's establishment in 2018.

Research Questions

- Would marginalized individuals access PWYW, and would privileged individuals misuse the model?
- Would clients choose to pay the lowest possible amount, or contribute what they could afford?
- Would providing low-cost therapy without conditions facilitate compliance for marginalized individuals?
- Was cost the sole factor influencing a client's choice of therapy provider?

Method

Design

This study employed an exploratory sequential mixed-methods approach. Participants were selected using non-probabilistic purposive sampling based on specific criteria.

Sample

Inclusion criteria: Participants aged 18 and above; clients who utilized the PWYW initiative at The Alternative Story; clients who began therapy between October 1, 2018, and September 30, 2020.

Exclusion criteria: Clients considered to have extremely sensitive or active concerns in therapy, such as Child Sexual Abuse, Complex Trauma, or Severe Mental Illnesses.

Data Collection

Participants were individually contacted and provided information about the study's purpose, procedure, and time commitment. Clients who used the PWYW initiative were approached by their therapists for permission to be contacted by a data-collection team member. After obtaining informed consent, participants completed a quantitative questionnaire.

The questionnaire captured demographic information to determine the client's social location in terms of gender, sexual orientation, caste, religion, annual income, disability, and available emotional and financial support. It also explored the impact of the PWYW model on mental health and overall quality of life.

Participants were subsequently invited to participate in an in-depth qualitative interview conducted online with AI transcription. The qualitative phase included 11 of the 31 quantitative participants, and aimed to understand what factors — beyond cost — led participants to choose The Alternative Story for therapy. Descriptive statistics and cross-tabular analyses were performed using Zoho Sheets and RStudio.

Results and Discussion

Sample Characteristics

The sample consisted of 31 participants, 11 of whom also participated in the qualitative phase. Most participants (20 out of 31) identified as female; 9 identified as male; and 2 did not identify with the gender binary. Eight out of 31 self-identified as being from the LGBTQIA++ community.

The sample was predominantly young, with 25 out of 31 participants aged 18 to 29 years. Five participants were between 30 and 39 years of age, and one was over 40.

In terms of annual income, nearly half the sample (15 out of 31) reported earning less than Rs. 1,80,000 per year — roughly equivalent to the minimum wage in Karnataka. Seven participants identified as belonging to marginalized castes (SC, ST, and OBC categories). Twenty-four out of 31 lived with a co-morbid health condition, and 20 out of 31 reported receiving no financial support from family or loved ones for their personal expenses.

Despite diversity in reported incomes, most participants lived with two or more marginalizations — conditions that negatively compound mental health and make sustained healthcare access particularly difficult.

Positive Impacts of the PWYW Model

Analysis revealed that almost all participants (29 out of 31) agreed that the PWYW model helped them access therapy regularly and focus on their mental health without adding undue financial burden. More than two-thirds (23 out of 31) said the model removed the initial financial hurdle that had previously delayed help-seeking. Additionally, 20 out of 30 participants agreed that the money saved could be redirected to address other life challenges.

Importantly, more than half the sample (18 out of 31) cited the organization's principled stance on accessibility and its commitment to creating a safe space for marginalized individuals as a crucial factor in their decision to seek therapy there — not cost alone. Fifteen out of 31 participants noted that the availability of therapists trained in issues faced by marginalized communities further inspired confidence, and 10 out of 31 first learned about the initiative through a favourable recommendation.

Chief Beneficiaries of the PWYW Model

A deeper examination of the data revealed patterns around who benefited most. Among the 20 women participants, 11 earned less than Rs. 1,80,000 per annum and 2 earned less than Rs. 3,00,000. Critically, all 13 of these women reported receiving no financial support from family for mental health expenses — meaning access to therapy would have been impossible without the PWYW model.

Among the 8 LGBTQIA++ participants, 7 out of 8 stated that the organization's ideology was as important a factor as the session cost. Many therapists practising at the organization belong to the LGBTQIA++ community and have disclosed this in their bios. Qualitative participants from this community described seeing same-community therapists offering PWYW services as creating a sense of safety and affirmation that previous therapy experiences had not provided. Others stated they would not have sought therapy at all without the PWYW model.

Sustainability of the PWYW Model

A key concern in introducing PWYW was financial sustainability. At the time of writing, the regular fee for an hour-long counselling session was Rs. 1,499, while PWYW allowed clients to pay between Rs. 299 and Rs. 1,499 per session according to their affordability.

The data showed that only 7 out of 31 participants paid the base price. The remaining 24 voluntarily paid above the base — 12 paid between Rs. 300 and Rs. 500, and 12 paid more than Rs. 500 per session. This demonstrates that clients did not default to the minimum, but rather sought to pay as much as they could while balancing other financial obligations. The model has thus taken a genuinely collaborative form: the organization trusted clients to use it fairly, and clients honoured that trust in the interest of the initiative's sustainability.

Limitations and Conclusions

Challenges of the PWYW Model

While the findings confirm manifold positive impacts, several challenges must be acknowledged:

- Any fee, however low, can deter healthcare access. A 2012 study in Haryana found that inpatient admission rates declined by nearly 24% in a district that introduced user fees, compared to near-static rates in a district without such fees (Prinja et al., 2012).
- For PWYW to be scalable, telemedicine is essential — but this requires significant ongoing infrastructure costs (equipment, software, high-speed internet) for both providers and clients. It also requires clients to be digitally literate and integrated into the banking system.
- Demand for PWYW sessions currently exceeds availability at the organization. Catering to total demand at PWYW cost would threaten the organization's financial viability.
- Service providers (counsellors) sometimes experience nominal session fees as devaluing their skills, and expect salaries comparable to peers at non-subsidized organizations — a burden that cannot be borne by PWYW revenue alone.
- Venture-capital-funded mental healthcare ventures that offer free or discounted services while paying above-market therapist salaries can capture talent and market share, potentially monopolizing the sector and setting future pricing terms.
- Outpatient mental health consultations are not covered by insurance in India. Counselling services are taxed at 18% GST under 'consulting services', as Counselling Psychologists are not recognized as 'Mental Health Professionals' under current legislation — preventing them from being classified as exempt healthcare providers.

Conclusions

The PWYW model is not proposed as a pan-India solution to the mental health care gap. Free and universal mental healthcare at the district and taluk levels remains the only sustainable path forward for the country.

However, the evidence presented here demonstrates that PWYW is a viable, equitable, and client-empowering alternative to sliding-scale models for private practitioners willing to dedicate a proportion of their slots to accessible care. The ownership clients feel over the model — and the collaborative trust it builds — is one of its most distinctive features.

Policy Recommendations

- Implement fair business practices for organizations offering PWYW or subsidized mental healthcare.
- Exempt counselling services from the Goods and Services Tax (GST).
- Formally recognize Counselling Psychologists as ‘Mental Health Professionals’ under India’s mental health legislation.
- Extend medical insurance coverage to outpatient mental health consultations.

These measures would go a long way in making models such as PWYW significantly easier to scale.

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References

- Anand, V., Verma, L., Aggarwal, A., Nanjundappa, P., & Rai, H. (2021). COVID-19 and psychological distress: Lessons for India. PLOS ONE, 16(8), e0255683. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0255683>
- Bhardwaj, S., & Devanand, A. (2021). Impact finance can help solve India’s mental health crisis. World Economic Forum.
- Birla, N. (2019). Mental health in India: 7.5% of country affected; less than 4,000 experts available. Economic Times.
- Desai, R. (2019). For young people with mental health struggles, therapy is a luxury. The Swaddle.
- Dhillon, K. (2020). Mind the treatment gap. Caravan Magazine.
- Express News Service. (2021). Bangladesh beats India in per capita income. New Indian Express.
- Goyal, R. (2020). Three years on, India’s progressive Mental Healthcare Act is dogged by gaps in implementation. Scroll.in.
- Joshi, G., & Sharma, G. (2020). Burnout: A risk factor amongst mental health professionals during COVID-19. Asian Journal of Psychiatry, 54, 102300.
- Kaur, R., & Pathak, R. P. (2017). Treatment gap in mental health: A review. Indian Journal of Psychiatry, 59(3), 262–268.
- Koshy, J., & Perappadan, B. (2018). Addressing mental health in rural India. The Hindu.
- Kunzler, A., Röthke, N., Günthner, L., Stoffers-Winterling, J., Tüscher, O., Coenen, M., et al. (2021). Mental burden and its risk and protective factors during the early phase of the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic. Globalization and Health, 17(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12992-021-00670-y>

Prinja, S., Aggarwal, A. K., Kumar, R., & Kanavos, P. (2012). User charges in health care: Evidence of effect on service utilization & equity from north India. *Indian Journal of Medical Research*, 136(5), 868–876.

Rajkumar, R. P. (2020). COVID-19 and mental health: A review of the existing literature. *Asian Journal of Psychiatry*, 52, 102066. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajp.2020.102066>

Rathore, U., & Khanna, S. (2021). Out of the frying pan and into the fire: Effects of COVID-19 crisis on small and medium enterprises (MSME) in India. Centre for Sustainable Employment.

Sagar, R., Dandona, R., Gururaj, G., Dhaliwal, R., Singh, A., Ferrari, A., et al. (2020). The burden of mental disorders across the states of India: The Global Burden of Disease Study 1990–2017. *The Lancet Psychiatry*, 7(2), 148–161. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s2215-0366\(19\)30475-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/s2215-0366(19)30475-4)

Sharma, P. (2019). Unaffordable mental healthcare puts additional stress on millennials. *Mint*.

Walsh, R., & Dasenbrook, N. (2008). The complications of sliding fee scales. *Counseling Today*.

World Health Organisation. (2018). *Mental health atlas 2017* (pp. 35–48). Geneva: WHO.